

ASTRAL

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Report

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1 Summary

This deliverable was created as part of the WP2 ‘New IMTA value chains and production methods’ of the EU H2020 All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) project and deals with the production value chain of IMTA Lab Ireland (Figure 1) adapted from Bostock et al.¹. Other aspects of the value chain are addressed in investigations and reports compiled by other Work Packages in ASTRAL (see ASTRAL deliverables 4.1, 4.4, 6.3, 7.7, <https://www.astral-project.eu/deliverables>). The deliverable provides information on the trials undertaken at the open water marine research site for each of the species produced at IMTA Lab Ireland.

The overall objective of IMTA Lab Ireland was to develop and validate cost-effective IMTA in an open water aquaculture production site. To achieve this objective, the cultivation environment was monitored to provide information on growth of the chosen species along with biosecurity, species health and system health monitoring. Trials to optimise culture technology using differing containment methods were undertaken. Data on the 11 trialled open water IMTA species was generated, which will positively support the uptake of IMTA by existing and future aquaculture producers both international and local. This information will enhance the sustainability of aquaculture into the future, as IMTA practices become a more common method of seafood production allowing the advancement of more circular production systems. These findings have contributed towards the development of new, sustainable, profitable, and resilient value chains for IMTA production within the ASTRAL project and within the framework of existing, emerging and potential Atlantic markets.

¹ Bostock, J., Lane, A., Hough, C. et al. *Aquacult Int* (2016) 24: 699. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-016-9992-1>

2 Introduction

This report details the outcomes of the species trials of the IMTA production value chain of IMTA lab Ireland (Figure 1), other aspects of the value chain are addressed in investigations and reports compiled by other Work Packages in ASTRAL (see ASTRAL deliverables 4.1, 4.4, 6.3, 7.7). All deliverables can be found on the ASTRAL website at <https://www.astral-project.eu/deliverables>.

Figure 1. IMTA lab Ireland Production Value Chain¹

ASTRAL

The EU H2020 project ASTRAL has developed new, sustainable, profitable and resilient value chains for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) production within the framework of existing, emerging and potential Atlantic markets. This project gathers four IMTA labs including open-water (Ireland, Scotland), land-based pump-ashore with partial (50 %) recirculation (South Africa) and recirculation 'biofloc' land-based (Brazil) systems and one prospective IMTA lab (Argentina), focusing on a regional challenge-based perspective, including fish, mollusc, echinoderm, crustacean and algae species. ASTRAL is assessing how to increase circularity using IMTA methods of cultivation by 50-60 % compared to monoculture aquaculture and will provide a circular business model, boosting revenue diversification for aquaculture producers increasing profitability by at least 30 %. New and improved innovative technology have been developed, including biosensors, sensors, Internet of Things (IoT) and an Artificial Intelligence (AI) data analytics platform have been validated at IMTA labs. Potential environmental and climatic risks for Northern and Southern Atlantic regions are being addressed,

delivering a monitoring programme and recommendations for Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs), pathogens and microplastics. ASTRAL is delivering an ambitious and gender-sensitive human capital development plan (HUCAP) which seeks to improve professional skills and create a highly trained workforce. This project gathers a collaborative ecosystem within the project framework bringing together and connecting industrial partners, SMEs, scientists, policy makers, social representatives and other relevant stakeholders promoting data exchange, knowledge sharing and business opportunities.

Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA)

IMTA is defined as the farming of aquaculture species from different trophic levels, and with complementary ecosystem functions in the same area or at the same site. This type of integrated culturing allows one species' uneaten feed, waste, and nutrients to be recaptured and converted into fertilizer and feed for the other aquaculture species. This approach takes advantage of synergistic interactions between species. The combination of fed aquaculture species (e.g., finfish or shrimp) with extractive aquaculture species, which utilizes the inorganic nutrients (e.g. seaweeds) and organic nutrients (e.g. suspension and deposit-feeders) allows growth in this type of system. IMTA aims to aid ecological balanced systems to improve environmental sustainability, enhance ecosystem services, boost economic stability by increasing biomass, lowering costs, providing product diversification, reducing risk, and creating jobs in rural communities while advancing societal acceptability².

ASTRAL IMTA Laboratories

The IMTA labs form the heart of the ASTRAL project, providing the context for developing cost-effective, profitable and sustainable IMTA production. The term 'IMTA labs' refers to the locations of the IMTA production sites and is not to be confused with a typical laboratory set up. The ASTRAL IMTA labs consist of recirculation, flow-through, open-water and land-based production systems. The locations of the ASTRAL IMTA labs are shown in Figure 2.

² Chopin, T. (2013). Aquaculture, Integrated Multi-trophic (IMTA). In: Christou, P., Savin, R., Costa-Pierce, B.A., Misztal, I., Whitelaw, C.B.A. (eds) Sustainable Food Production. Springer, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-5797-8_173

Figure 2. Locations of IMTA labs around the Atlantic Ocean

3 Open Water IMTA

IMTA production can be carried out in a number of differing aquaculture systems. Open water IMTA, as carried out in the ASTRAL project in IMTA lab Ireland, refers to species production at sea with mooring structures in place to anchor the growing structures to the seabed. This type of system is continuously exposed to the ambient environmental conditions including wind and wave action. Figure 3 shows a potential IMTA set up in open water.

Figure 3. Schematic of potential IMTA scenario. ©Marine Institute

3.1 Site description

Lehanagh Pool Research site is a coastal aquaculture installation located 0.25 km from the shore in Bertraghboy Bay, on the West Coast of Ireland (Figure 4). The site is a licensed 23.3 hectares multi-species research site. It is a fully experimental, non-commercial cultivation site operated by the Marine Institute. The site is within a sheltered enclosed area to the inner most part of Bertraghboy Bay that is predominantly shallow (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Location of Irish IMTA lab Lehanagh Pool and Mace Head data buoy.

The location is relatively sheltered with no significant fetch or swell and waves are produced by local wind conditions (Figure 5). It is located approximately 1 km from the nearest pier used for site access. There are two estuarine inputs, Cachel Bay and the river Gowla. The location of the site in the Connemara area of Ireland, is subjected to runoff from rainfall, reducing salinity and increasing turbidity with high particulate loading. Due to runoff, salinity ranges from 24 to 35 psu but is typically > 32 psu. Tidal range is approximately 5 m, depth of the site ranges from 15 m to 20 m and water temperature ranges from 5 to 18 °C. The mean current speeds are 0.040 and 0.028 m/s for mid-water and seabed, respectively, and residual currents and directions are 0.028 m/s at 171° and 0.015 m/s at 180° for mid-water and seabed, respectively. These low current flow rates indicate little dispersive capacity for fish cage waste, to maximise uptake of released nutrients, IMTA species would need to be co-located to primary source. Any discharge from the cages at this site is likely to be dispersed initially to the south and any particulate wastes would be deposited to the seabed close to the cages.

Figure 5. Image of Lehanagh Pool research site looking north-east to south-west in direction of prevailing current. ©Marine Institute

Infrastructure on site consists of a traditional 50 m circumference pen grid for fish culture (Figure 5 & 6). This scaled down approach is approximately a quarter of the size of a commercial Irish salmon farm as the site operates for research purposes only. To the south-east of the pen grid, there is an attached Low Trophic Grid (LTG) (Figure 6) consisting of a submerged rectangular grid (size) with capacity for ca. 780 m suspended longlines.

Figure 6. Engineer drawings of LTG, moored as an annex to the existing salmon pen grid.

A 14-day simulation of Marine Institute Bertraghboy model with particle tracking for upper, mid and bottom simulations was completed to assess nutrient dispersion sourced from fish waste at the pens. Based on the results of this model, the new infrastructure is orientated south-east of the pen grid (indicated in red in Figure 7). The location was chosen downstream of the modelled nutrient plume, in order to maximize potential for uptake of nutrients from the fed species at the site.

Figure 7. Heat map of particle tracking modelled of nutrients released from salmon pen indicated by the red dot. Black line indicates site boundary. ©Marine Institute

This new LTG is moored as an annex to the existing grid structure (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Surface image of low trophic grid on site fully stocked with all species. Colour floats used to indicate stocks. ©Marine Institute

The new low trophic grid is designed to create a pathway for current monoculture facilities to 'add' productivity. The grid model aims to maximize available space and minimize environmental impacts. The design allows the operator to adjust orientation, depths, and spacing of culture lines using multiple attachment points to facilitate a range of low trophic species. As the grid structure is submerged there is less visual impact, suspended culture limits interaction with the benthic environment and by utilising

the main grid for fish culture, the co-location maximises uptake of nutrients released from fish rearing activities and reduces the number of anchor points by 50 % when compared to traditional longlines.

By creating this new structure there is increased habitat and biodiversity at the site for low trophic species, and a reduction in the environmental nutrient load, delivering a healthier production system.

This novel set-up maximises the use of space at this site and adds to the development of circularity within the production system. Careful consideration is given to the materials used to balance longevity of components, with appropriate end of life disposal such as recycling and renewables. The design also allows multiple uses for single pieces of infrastructure, future proofing, and planning for continued sustainable research at the site. Table 1 includes the materials required for the construction of the LTG.

Table 1. Details of equipment used to create the LTG grid at Lehanagh Pool Marine Research site.

Equipment description	Material
Damper buoys 1100l	Rotomolded PE and filled with Polystyrene foam. Density foam 25 kg/m ³ i.e. 580 l =21,25 kg of foam and remaining material is LLPE (51,755 kg)
Grid rings - round steel ring - masterlink 6" x 4"	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Ultraflex Aqua Plus 40 mm mooring rope with hard eyes 50 m	Polypropelene
Ultraflex polysteel 14 mm heel rope	Polysteel
OCEANFLEX unleaded 24 mm polypropelene riser rope	Polypropelene
Galvanised steel anchors	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Galvanised steel chain 19 mm; 3 m	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Heavy duty galvanised steel chain 5 m	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Bow shackle 6.5 T	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Bow shackle 9.5 T	Heavy duty galvanised steel
32 mm grid rope with dyneema soft splice locks	Dyneema

A full catalogue of species trialled at the IMTA lab Ireland can be seen in the Table 2 below.

Table 2. Species cultivated at the Irish IMTA lab

<u>Common name</u>	<u>Latin name</u>	<u>Role in IMTA</u>
Lumpfish	<i>Cyclopterus lumpus</i>	Fed species
Ballan wrasse	<i>Labrus bergylta</i>	Fed species
Atlantic salmon	<i>Salmo salar</i>	Fed species
Atlantic wakame	<i>Alaria esculenta</i>	Extractive Species
Sugar kelp	<i>Saccharina latissima</i>	Extractive Species
Black or Variegated scallop/Cluisín	<i>Mimachlamys varia</i>	Extractive Species
European lobster	<i>Homarus gammarus</i>	Novel species
King scallop	<i>Pecten maximus</i>	Extractive Species
Native oyster/European flat oyster	<i>Ostrea edulis</i>	Extractive Species
Purple sea urchin	<i>Paracentrotus lividus</i>	Extractive Species
Sea cucumber	<i>Holothuria forskali</i>	Extractive Species

The species at the IMTA lab Ireland (Figure 9) are categorized as: fed, extractive, benthic scavengers or novel species.

1. Fed species: Feed is inputted to the system for Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), also lumpfish (*Cyclopterus lumpus*) and Ballan wrasse (*Labrus bergylta*) when stocked. As a result, the fish release waste/nutrients into the surrounding water.
2. Extractive species: There are two types of extractive species. The filter feeders; Great scallop (*Pecten maximus*), Cluisin (*Mimchlamys varia*) and Native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*), filter out particulate waste from the water as food, reusing the waste from the fish from the environment. Dissolved 'waste' is extracted by seaweeds *Saccharina latissima* and *Alaria esculenta* by absorbing dissolved minerals and carbon, reusing the 'waste' from the fish and shellfish entering the environment.
3. Benthic scavengers: Sea cucumber (*Holothuria forskali*) removes particulates from the upper surface of benthic sediments on the seafloor. This particulate waste contains uneaten food and particulate waste from the fish.
4. Novel species: European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) utilise fish waste prevalent in the water column but also graze on the community structure established in the holding baskets. However, they are not

grown to market size; instead, they are released as juveniles as a stock enhancement initiative linking coastal industries. Spiny sea urchins (*Paracentrotus lividus*) are fed with the seaweeds grown in the IMTA process. They are incorporated into the food chain by manual feeding, this process enhances the circularity of this IMTA production system.

Figure 9. Image of IMTA lab Ireland with graphics overlaid to show the co-location of species at the site.
©Marine Institute

3.1.1 Cultivation Environment

Throughout the study period, environmental parameters of the production site were monitored. This data was gathered using several different sensors situated at various locations and depths onsite. The following gives a breakdown of the environment at Lehanagh Pool from 2021-2024 and shows the variability in the environment which can impact species growth in the open water system. Abiotic data gives a crucial insight to the culturing environment. This is particularly useful as some species are more susceptible to certain conditions or thrive in others.

3.1.1.1 Wind speed

Wind speed and maximum gusts (m/s) were downloaded from the Mace Head (Figure 10) data buoy (https://erddap.marine.ie/erddap/tabledap/compass_mace_head.html). The data buoy network is managed by the Marine Institute in collaboration with Met Éireann and the UK Met Office. The Irish Weather Buoy Network is designed to improve weather forecasts and safety at sea around Ireland. The buoy network provides vital data for weather forecasts, shipping bulletins, gale and swell warnings as well as data for general public information and research. This enabled an indication of gale force winds and storm events from 2021 to 2023 of the ASTRAL project. Met Éireann report storm and violent storm events in November and December of 2021 with named storms Arwen and Barra. Barra was reported as reaching up to 104 km/h at Mace Head (orange arrow, Figure 10).

Figure 10. Wind speed (A) and Maximum gust (B) in m/s detected at Mace Head Marine Institute data buoy 2021.

Met Éireann report storm and violent storm events in February 2022 with named storms Eunice and Franklin. Storm Franklin was measured as 102 km/h on the Mace Head buoy (orange arrow, Figure 11).

Figure 11. Wind speed (C) and Maximum gust (D) in m/s detected at Mace Head Marine Institute data buoy 2022.

In 2023, the data buoy at Mace Head went through repairs, during this time no wind speed data was gathered. Met Éireann report storm force events on 10th December 2023 with named storm Fergus, reaching 91 km/h (orange arrow, Figure 12). This is followed by two more storms in January 2024, storms Isha and Jocelyn, that reached gusts of 106 km/h and 96 km/h respectively.

Storm events have the potential to cause damage to Lehanagh Pool infrastructure or disrupt maintenance or work needed onsite. The occurrence of storm events also has the potential to impede growth of the low trophic IMTA species, in particular the seaweeds, due to disturbance to the longlines.

Figure 12. Wind speed (E) and Maximum gust (F) in m/s detected at Mace Head Marine Institute data buoy 2023.

3.1.1.2 Water Currents

A Valeport MIDAS CTD+ (current meter) was deployed at Lehanagh pool to measure the current speeds on site. It was deployed at the surface and measured at a depth of approximately 4m. At this depth, typical directional flow is from east to west +/- 35°. The highest velocity was measured at 1.93 m/s in February 2021 during a spring tide (Table 3. Example of current velocity measured by Midas Current Meter in February 2021.). More typical flows display velocities closer to the average flow on site (0.058 m/s).

Table 3. Example of current velocity measured by Midas Current Meter in February 2021.

Parameter	Velocity (m/s)
Max X (horizontal plane)	1.933
Min X (horizontal plane)	0.000
Average X (horizontal plane)	0.058
Average Y (Vertical plane)	0.012

3.1.1.3 Dissolved Oxygen

Dissolved oxygen (DO) was measured during routine monitoring of salmon welfare at the salmon pens. DO was measured at the surface using Oxyguard Handy Polaris hand-held meter. In 2021, DO ranged from 88 – 110%, in 2022 it ranged from 88 – 107.2 %, in 2023 the range was 88.3 – 109.8 % and in the first half of 2024 was measured as 88.1 – 98 %.

All DO data can be found on Zenodo SharePoint at: <https://zenodo.org/records/12187108>

3.1.1.4 Water nutrient levels

Water samples were taken from two locations (middle (M) of salmon pens and southwest (SW) of salmon pens) onsite and collected at three depths (1 m, 3 m and 10 m) using a Van Dorn water sampler (Figure 13). These samples were then sent to a certified laboratory (Complete Laboratory Solutions <https://cls.ie/>), for the determination of concentrations of orthophosphate; nitrate; nitrite; ammonia and chlorophyll-a. In sampling years 2021-2023 water samples were tested monthly from March to December. In 2021, chlorophyll-a was found to increase within the water column (Figure 14) in March at sites M-10, SW-1 and SW-10 and throughout June to August. At all other times of the year concentrations were below the limit of detection (<0.001). In 2021, nitrite was found to be <0.004 mg/l, nitrate had a range of <0.003 - 0.065 mg/l, orthophosphate was recorded as 0.004 - 0.022 mg/l and ammonia <0.001 - 0.032 mg/l. In 2022, chlorophyll-a was recorded on all water samples apart from SW-10 (Figure 15). An increase to a maximum of 4.01 µg/l was measured in August at M-10, this was the highest amount of chlorophyll-a recorded in the three years of monitoring. Other results from 2022 showed nitrite to have a range of <0.003 - 0.006 mg/l, nitrate was recorded onsite as <0.003 - 0.091 mg/l, orthophosphate as <0.003 - 0.018 mg/l and ammonia as <0.001 - 0.032 mg/l. In 2023, chlorophyll-a was present in detectable concentrations from April to September at all sampling locations (Figure 16). Nitrite and nitrate ranged from <0.003 - 0.048 mg/l, orthophosphate from <0.003 - 0.013 mg/l and ammonia as <0.001 - 0.018 mg/l.

Figure 13. Aerial image of Lehanagh fish cages and location of monthly water sampling. Green circle is M or middle of the site; yellow circle is SW or south west of the site.

All water column nutrient data at each sampling location and depth can be found on Zenodo SharePoint at: [10.5281/zenodo.10949672](https://zenodo.org/record/10949672).

Phytoplankton was sampled randomly on site in 2021 and 2022 by Marine Institute phytoplankton monitoring³. Observed in abundance in July 2021 was a healthy mix of diatoms *Leptocylindrus danicus* 15,000 cells per litre and *Chaetoceros* (Hyalochaete) spp. 60,000 cells per litre. Observed in abundance in August 2021 samples were *Leptocylindrus danicus* 36,000 and 212,000. 859,807 cells/l of *Microflagellate* sp. were observed in September 2021 sample. Samples analysed in February 2022 had a healthy abundance of diatoms which you would expect as it's the start of the spring bloom (*Skeletonema* spp.) 14,440 cells/l.

³ <https://www.marine.ie/site-area/areas-activity/marine-environment/phytoplankton-monitoring>

Figure 14. Chlorophyll-a in $\mu\text{g/l}$ at each sampling location (M, SW) and depth (1, 3 and 10 m) in 2021.

Figure 15. Chlorophyll-a in $\mu\text{g/l}$ at each sampling location (M, SW) and depth (1, 3 and 10 m) in 2022.

Figure 16. Chlorophyll-a in $\mu\text{g/l}$ at each sampling location (M, SW) and depth (1,3 and 10 m) in 2023.

3.1.1.5 Temperature

Water temperature was recorded using HOBO® UTBI-001 data logger (TidbiT v2) placed at 4 m depth intervals from 1 m to 16 m in the middle of the site at Lehanagh Pool. Temperature data was recorded on an hourly basis providing a depth profile for each year of the study. In 2021, the minimum water temperature recorded was in February as 4.77 °C at 1 m depth and the maximum temperature was recorded in July as 20.63 °C also at 1 m depth (Figure 17). In 2022, the minimum water temperature was 6.28 °C at 1 m in December and the maximum was 19.69 °C at 1 m in August (Figure 18). In 2023, the minimum temperature was recorded as 5.87 °C in January and the maximum as 19.86 °C in July, both at 1 m depth (Figure 19). In the first half of 2024, the minimum temperature was recorded as 6.56 °C at 1 m depth in January and the maximum 13.5 °C in May.

Temperature data collected by IMTA lab Ireland at Lehanagh Pool can be accessed here: [ERDDAP - ICTempNetwork 2251 f301 32e1 \(marine.ie\)](https://erddap.marine.ie/ICTempNetwork_2251_f301_32e1)

Figure 17. Temperature profile of Lehanagh Pool in 2021.

Figure 18. Temperature profile of Lehanagh Pool in 2022.

Figure 19. Temperature profile of Lehanagh Pool in 2023.

3.1.1.6 Salinity

Freshwater influence due to the hydrodynamic regime at Lehanagh Pool and heavy rainfall can cause freshwater to accumulate at the surface. This can result in a drop in salinity at the surface and can cause decreased light penetration due to high particulate organic matter and suspended solids. In extended periods this has the potential to impede the growth of stocks. Daily salinity checks were conducted to monitor this.

In 2021, salinity was measured in conjunction with the water nutrient sampling, providing a salinity value at three different depths in two localities (M-1-10 and SW-1-10, see Figure 13). Figure 20 shows the variation in salinity (psu) values at each sampling location, these samples were taken from March to December. It shows that salinity at the shallower depths (1 m and 3 m) can be affected by freshwater with a larger range than those sampled deeper (10 m). The lowest salinity values (<30 psu) were recorded in March, October, November and December 2021. The highest salinity values (>34 psu) were recorded in July and September 2021. In following years, salinity was measured using a hand held refractometer at salmon pens at the surface during routine welfare monitoring of salmon stock. In 2022, salinity ranged from 27 – 35 psu, in 2023 salinity measured ranged from 25 – 36 psu and in the first half of 2024 ranged from 28 – 34 psu.

Figure 20. Density ridge plot displaying salinity values (psu) at 6 sampling localities at Lehanagh Pool from March to December 2021.

Salinity data at can be found on Zenodo SharePoint at: <https://zenodo.org/records/12188929>

3.1.1.7 Light Intensity

HOBO Pendant® MX2202 data loggers were deployed on site to monitor light intensity (in lux = lumens/m²). These loggers were attached to lobster growing structures and seaweed lines at varying depths during the trials. Figure 21 displays the light intensity measured in 2023 at 5 m depth. Biofouling can cover the sensor surface and interfere with light measurements, ideally data loggers should be cleaned every day, however this proved to be unachievable during these trials due to challenges of inclement weather and staff time resources. This plot shows that when cleaning had occurred (e.g. mid-April) lux readings increased. However, during periods where the sensors became fouled, light levels were found to be lower. Figure 22 displays the lux measurement from seaweed growing line at 2 m depth in the same year. However, the light measured is lower than that recorded at 5 m, which is not accurate. Again, it was evident that the sensor had been impacted by shadowing by the growing seaweed leading to inaccurate data recordings. In future, these types of sensors need

to be situated away from growing structures and kept clean and free from interference from species growth.

Figure 21. Light intensity (lux) at 5 m depth (HOBO logger deployed from lobster structure).

Figure 22. Light (lux) measurement at 2 m depth (HOBO logger on seaweed line 2023).

All light data at each sampling location and depth can be found on Zenodo SharePoint at:

<https://zenodo.org/records/12187343>

4 Species

4.1 Atlantic Salmon *Salmo salar*

4.1.1 Introduction

Salmon aquaculture started at an experimental level in the 1960s, since then it has grown substantially with consumption of seafood more than doubled per capita between 1961 and 2015⁴. To meet this demand today, approximately 70% of salmon produced for consumption is being farmed worldwide⁵ and worldwide production exceeds 3 million tonnes⁶. The salmon aquaculture industry has traditionally been dominated by a few farming regions in Chile, Norway, Canada and Scotland. Ireland contributes to the sector with over 12,844 tonnes of Atlantic salmon produced organically from 2019⁷. To ensure the successful production of Atlantic salmon feed is inputted to the system, this is fed routinely to the salmon stock and as a result waste/nutrients are generated which enter the surrounding water. The Lehanagh Pool production system allows for the circularity capabilities of the IMTA process, salmon waste which is particularly rich in nitrogen and phosphorous becomes a valuable resource for extractive species (see Deliverable 4.2). Bioremediation of nutrients is the key pillar in circularity performance of this system with salmon as its top fed species⁸.

The production methods for this species can be found in ASTRAL Deliverable 2.8.

4.1.2 Welfare Assessment of Salmon

The welfare and wellbeing of fish is a prominent issue in a fish farming and plays a key role in many of the decisions made on a daily basis and throughout the production cycle. In the assessment of welfare of Atlantic salmon welfare at Lehanagh Pool, the handbook compiled by Nofima has been interpreted for use at this production site⁹. This provides detailed descriptions of the methods to assess fish welfare. Welfare indicators can either be direct i.e. measurements and observations from the fish, or indirect system-based e.g. measurements and observations of the production environment. Welfare indicators that can be assessed on a farm are deemed more practicable and are termed Operational Welfare Indicators (OWIs).

⁴ GSI Handbook 2020, Sustainable Salmon Farming the Future of Food.

https://globalsalmoninitiative.org/files/documents/GSI_Handbook_2020.pdf

⁵ <https://globalsalmoninitiative.org/en/about-salmon-farming/#:~:text=The%20salmon%20farming%20production%20cycle,to%20be%20prepared%20for%20sale>

⁶ <https://www.fao.org/3/cc0461en/cc0461en.pdf>

⁷ <https://bim.ie/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Annual-Aquaculture-report-2022.pdf>

⁸ Checa, D.; Macey, B.M.; Bolton, J.J.; Brink-Hull, M.; O'Donohoe, P.; Cardozo, A.; Poersch, L.H.; Sánchez, I. Circularity Assessment in Aquaculture: The Case of Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) Systems. *Fishes* 2024, *9*, 165.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/fishes9050165>

⁹ Noble, C. et al. *Welfare Indicators for Farmed Atlantic Salmon - Tools for Assessing Fish Welfare*. pp351 (2018).

4.1.3 Application of OWIs

Each welfare indicator is divided into levels from good to bad welfare and the results are typically represented as the distribution of sampled fish. The indicators can be used as an early warning system, alerting the farmer that something is potentially wrong and warrants further investigation before mortality begins to increase. Table 4 lists the criteria used to assess and monitor the status of salmon stocks throughout the IMTA trials.

Table 4. Welfare Indicators used to monitor salmon health.

Welfare Indicators (units) measured for individual salmon	
Fork Length (cm)	Lesions (1-3)
Weight (g)	Sea lice infestation (1-3)
Eye (1-3)	Vertebral deformity (1-3)
Fins (1-3)	Opercular damage (1-3)
Skin (1-3)	Opercular damage healed or active
AGD score	Opercular deformation (1-3)
Gill necrosis (0-4)	Snout damage (1-3)
Emaciation (1-3)	Jaw deformity (1-3)
Scale loss (0-3)	Mucous (1-3)
Smoltified (Y/N)	AGD swan no.

4.1.4 Results

In calculating the relative OWI scores, the scores from a sample of 30 fish were pooled to produce an average between 0-3. The size of the number does not indicate that the welfare status is poor or good but rather highlighted when there is a change/deterioration in welfare following a certain event.

Some parameters are grouped together, e.g. eye scores encompassed cataracts, eye haemorrhages and exophthalmia; and upper and lower jaw deformities were grouped into simpler jaw deformity. Elevated mean welfare number during summer 2022 was observed (Figure 23). There is a slightly elevated number in the period from July to August 2023 (Figure 24). For remaining trial periods OWI number remains consistent.

Figure 23. Mean sample operational welfare Indicator (OWI) - Salmon

Figure 24. Condition factor - Salmon

4.1.5 Discussion and Conclusion

Salmon stocks at Lehanagh Pool grew well throughout each of the trials. Salmon play an important role in the trophic relationships of this open water system as the feed and waste from the salmon form the source of the nutrient flow across the IMTA system¹⁰. The positioning of the LTG next to the salmon pens allowed for the flow of nutrients to be targeted towards the lower trophic species.

The welfare of the salmon stocks was monitored and found to be in good health, with few indications of welfare fluctuations. During the Spring and Summer months as water temperatures begins to rise, potential infestations of sea lice and the development of Amoebic Gill Disease (AGD) begin to occur. An increase in the OWI rating was observed in June 2022, this occurred during a time of increased lice and AGD pressures. There was also evidence of a slightly elevated number in the period from July to August 2023, this coincides with poor condition factors, this again, coincided with increased pressures from sea lice infestation and AGD presence. For remaining trial periods OWI number remains consistent indicating that the salmon stocks were healthy with no insults or decrease in health observed.

¹⁰ Baltadakis, A., Casserly, J., Falconer, L., Sprague, M. & Telfer, T.C. 2020. European lobsters utilise Atlantic salmon wastes in coastal integrated multi-trophic aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture Environment Interactions* 12, 485-494. <https://doi.org/10.3354/aei00378>

4.2 Cleaner fish – Lumpfish *Cyclopterus lumpus* and Ballan wrasse *Labrus bergylta*

4.2.1 Introduction

The deployment of cleaner fish as a biological solution to maintain low sea lice levels among farmed Atlantic salmon is currently common industry practice, particularly among organically certified salmon farmers. In this trial the use of Lumpfish *Cyclopterus lumpus*, and Ballan wrasse *Labrus bergylta*, were employed to manage sea lice infestation. Lumpfish require a smooth surface to adhere to, by means of its unique sucker disc on its abdomen. They are provided with hides to serve as a refuge to which they have the option to stick when not actively feeding (refer to ASTRAL Deliverable D2.8). The Ballan wrasse are docile, shy fish, which, like the lumpfish, shelters among these hides. Both species browse/hunt from these hides. Specified food for the cleaner fish was provided to maintain the health and welfare of the cleaner fish.

4.2.2 Operational welfare indicators for cleaner fish

The welfare guidelines that have been used to monitor the welfare of the salmon stocks have been adapted to monitor the welfare of the cleaner fish on site (Table 5). Lumpfish were deployed at Lehanagh Pool during the Winter months in 2021 and 2023. Hatchery-reared Ballan wrasse were deployed at Lehanagh Pool in the Summer of 2023, this was the first time that this species of cleaner fish were deployed at this production site. The following parameters were grouped, e.g. eye scores encompassed cataracts, eye haemorrhages and exophthalmia; and upper and lower jaw deformities were grouped into simpler jaw deformity.

Table 5. Operational Welfare Indicators monitored for Lumpfish and Ballan wrasse.

Welfare indicators - lumpfish	Welfare indicators - wrasse
Number of sea lice	Emaciation
Caudal fin erosion	Skin lesions/wounds
Dorsal and pectoral fin erosion	Scale loss
Skin congestion	Eye damage
Skin discoloration	Opercular damage
Sucker deformity	Snout damage
Cataracts/Eyes	Vertebral deformities
Gills	Jaw deformity
Head snout skin	Sea lice infection
Emaciation	Active/healed fin damage

4.2.3 Results

A range of condition factors were observed from the two different Winter deployments of lumpfish (Mean: 6.02 ± 0.92 ; Minimum: 3.20; Maximum: 8.90; Range: 5.70, Figure 25). A range of welfare scores were obtained from the lumpfish (Mean: 0.06 ± 0.21 ; Minimum: 0.00; Maximum: 0.94; Range: 0.94, Figure 26).

Figure 25. Condition factor Lumpfish. Calculated using standard length.

Figure 26. Mean Lumpfish operational welfare indicator (OWI).

The results were based on a single deployment of Ballan wrasse during the summer of 2023. There was a small downward trend in mean condition factor over the course of their deployment (Figure 27). Acquiring a large sample number proved difficult. Nonetheless, the fish that were sampled had little or no obvious damage or changes in welfare scores. Healed fin erosion was evident on most fish (Figure 28).

Figure 27. Ballan wrasse condition factor.

Figure 28. Mean operational welfare indicator - Ballan wrasse

Sea lice levels on the salmon were counted on a regular basis at Lehanagh Pool, control remained effective especially in periods when cleaner fish were stocked (Figure 29).

Figure 29. Mean sea lice *Lepeophtheirus salmonis* counts from 2021 to 2024, lumpfish input highlighted in blue, wrasse input highlighted in yellow.

All sea lice data can be found on Zenodo SharePoint at: <https://zenodo.org/records/11657933>

4.2.4 Discussion and Conclusion

Both species of cleaner fish grew successfully during the IMTA trials. Their function as biological agents to control seal ice infestations were found to be successful. This site is positioned in the inner part of Bertraghboy Bay which is home to a commercial salmon farm in the outer reaches of the bay. Sea lice levels were controlled throughout the trials in accordance with the licence conditions.

The welfare of both cleaner fish species was monitored and results proved favourable for the health status on each species, however, it was difficult to obtain a full sample of Ballan wrasse as they are difficult to catch due to their shy nature. Among the fish that were caught, few OWI scores above zero were observed except for healed fin erosion which derived from the hatchery stage of production. Improved capture techniques, namely baited fishing pots, are recommended for any future deployments of Ballan wrasse.

Similar to the Ballan wrasse, healed tail erosion originating from their time at the hatchery among the lumpfish was pervasive so that the total fish length could not be used to generate a reliable condition factor. As a result, standard length (measuring the length of the fish from the tip of the mouth to the base of the tail) was used to generate the condition factors as this eliminates any confounding

measurements derived from the eroded caudal/tail fin. This condition factor was used to compare relative changes in group welfare. However, more detailed research is required to establish what value constitutes a healthy condition factor before any conclusions can be drawn on its use as a predictor of welfare.

4.3 Seaweed *Alaria esculenta* and *Saccharina latissima*

4.3.1 Introduction

Seaweed aquaculture is not a new innovation, in fact seaweed has been cultivated in Asia for centuries. However, its demand is now spreading rapidly and world production has grown almost three times to what it was 20 years ago: 10.6 million tonnes to 32.4 million tonnes¹¹. It is currently the fastest growing aquaculture industry globally. The majority of this seaweed production is now represented by farmed species. Macroalgal and microalgae species are grown for a multitude of purposes including for human nutrition, biofuel, agriculture (feed and fertiliser/biostimulants) and as ingredients for products. In Ireland, cultured longlines of seaweed have been grown since the 1990s. However, seaweed harvested from the shore still dominates over production on longlines¹². Another use for seaweed quickly gaining interest globally, is the ability of macroalgae to sequester carbon, helping to mitigate against climate change. Ocean afforestation (cultivation of seaweed forests on a large scale in ocean environments) is in its infancy¹³, however seaweed aquaculture also has the potential to offset carbon. Recent analysis has shown that seaweed farms can sequester carbon in marine sediment at a median net of approximately 0.5 tonnes of CO₂ equiv./ha¹⁴.

As an extractive species, seaweeds absorb dissolved inorganic nutrients from their surrounding environment, making them an ideal candidate for IMTA systems. The ability of seaweed to reduce the nutrient load from fed species, benefitting the environment through bioremediation and adding to the circular economy makes it a potentially important species group for the aquaculture sector worldwide¹⁵

4.3.2 Trial Methodology

The aim of this trial was to assess the potential to grow kelp species on longlines situated close to finfish cages. To monitor biomass and morphology of kelp species grown on longlines and report on observations for optimal growth. Finally, to assess how cultivation conditions effect growth of both species. In each year of the ASTRAL project, a trial for kelp species *Alaria esculenta* and *Saccharina latissima* was conducted. A total of four trials were run, seeded line (2mm) was sourced from Bord lascaigh Mhara, at the Bantry Marine Research Station Ltd in south-west Ireland and transferred to longlines at Lehanagh Pool. All four trials followed the same methodology, species were grown

¹¹ <https://asc-aqua.org/learn-about-seafood-farming/farmed-seaweed/>

¹² <https://bim.ie/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/BIM-IMAS-Strategy.pdf>

¹³ Ross, F., Tarbuck, P., & Macreadie, P. I. (2022). Seaweed afforestation at large-scales exclusively for carbon sequestration: Critical assessment of risks, viability and the state of knowledge. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9, 2269.

¹⁴ Analysis of farmed seaweed carbon crediting and novel markets to help decarbonise supply chains. The Nature Conservancy. <https://www.nature.org/content/dam/tnc/nature/en/documents/SeaweedMarketsAnalysis.pdf>

¹⁵ Thierry Chopin & Albert G. J. Tacon (2020): Importance of Seaweeds and Extractive Species in Global Aquaculture Production, *Reviews in Fisheries Science & Aquaculture*, DOI: 10.1080/23308249.2020.1810626

between 0.5 - 2 m depth. Biomass and morphology were measured each month during the growing period (February/March – May/June). For more information on the methodology of growing seaweed, see D2.8.

Trial 1: The first trial was run from October 2020 to May 2021 (2020 stock). *Alaria esculenta* only.

Trial 2: The second trial was run from October 2021 to May 2022 (2021 stock). Both species.

Trial 3: The third trial was run from October 2022 to May 2023 (2022 stock). Both species.

A control (CTRL) line of *Saccharina latissima* was deployed 150 m away from salmon cages.

Trial 4: The final trial was run from October 2023 to May/June 2024 (2023 stock). Both species.

A control (CTRL) line of *Alaria esculenta* was deployed 150 m away from salmon cages.

Growing structure locations for seaweed were placed on the LTG and a longline close to salmon pens and at a control site situated 150 m away from the flow of by-products from salmon cages (Figure 30). During these trials a sample of each species was sent away for nutritional analysis, specifically to test for content such as protein, carbohydrate, fat and other nutritional components. See D4.2 for further information on the circularity assessment carried out at Lehanagh Pool.

Figure 30. Aerial photo of the Lehanagh Pool Marine Research site in 2022. Red lines indicate location of the seaweed lines in relation to salmon cages.

To measure biomass, a monthly sample (= all biomass growing in 0.5 m line areas) was taken from each line, a total biomass was then calculated by extrapolating into kg/m. The six largest fronds from

the sample were measured for length (mm) and width (mm) and morphology of the seaweed was examined (Figure 31).

Figure 31. Example of kelp species *Alaria esculenta* on a longline (left) and Kelp fronds of *Saccharina latissima* measured in the lab (right)

4.3.3 Results

Trial 1

Alaria esculenta (referred to as *Alaria* from here) was the first kelp species trialled at Lehanagh Pool. Sampling of the crop began in January, biomass increased in every sampling period until harvest in April, when it reached >4 kg/m. (Figure 32).

Figure 32. Peak biomass (kg/m) of *Alaria esculenta* recorded in sampling periods of 2021.

Trial 2

Biomass was calculated from February to harvest, which was May for *Alaria* and June for *Saccharina latissima* (referred to as *Saccharina* from here). Both species displayed exponential growth at the end of March and into April. Thereafter, both species saw a decline in its growth. Both species produced biomass over 6.0 kg/m in this trial (Figure 33).

Figure 33. Peak biomass (kg/m) recorded for both species in sampling periods 2022.

Trial 3

Both *Alaria* and *Saccharina* were harvested at the end of April in 2023, *Alaria* had begun to rot at the end of the fronds and if left until May, would not have been in a condition to continue biomass and morphology measurements. Figure 34 shows the highest amount of biomass measured for each species at each sampling period. *Saccharina* had the most biomass reaching over 7 kg/m. *Alaria* did not perform as well as in other years, producing over 2 kg/m compared to over 6 kg/m in 2022 harvest. The CTRL of *Saccharina* produced a biomass of >4 kg/m.

Figure 34. Peak biomass (kg/m) recorded for each species sampled in all locations in 2023 and a CTRL line of *Saccharina*.

All growing lines were found to have patchy growth with small areas without any growth. Only the CTRL line that was away from any other infrastructure had growth across the entire line.

Trial 4

Seed source was available a month earlier for *Alaria* than *Saccharina* at stocking for this trial. Therefore, *Alaria* lines were seeded a month before *Saccharina* in October and November respectively. Due to two back-to-back storm events at the beginning of 2024, the less established *Saccharina* was impacted more severely. The seeded string wound onto one longline at the edge of the LTG was found to be snapped and the sporophytes were not able to attach and therefore the seed was lost. Other lines were found to have crossed causing abrasion along sections of longline, meaning attachment of sporophytes and development of the seaweed was impeded. In this sampling season, longlines were set-up with a colour coded system to the buoys connected to each line. It was therefore clear to see that lines could cross in bad weather conditions causing patchy growth again in this trial.

Despite the crossing of lines, both species produced a crop of seaweed comparable to other trials.

Figure 35. Peak biomass (kg/m) recorded for each species sampled in all locations in 2024 and a CTRL line of *Alaria*.

Alaria had the greatest growth between February and March sampling periods. Figure 35 shows that the CTRL line situated 150 m away from the other longlines had the best growth overall but dropped off more than that sampled on the LTG longlines. In April, *Alaria* had begun to rot at the ends and in June biofouling was present. Therefore, peak biomass for *Alaria* in this trial was end of March.

Saccharina greatest growth occurred from March onwards and continued to increase at every sampling. Despite the issues with weather and patchy growth, seaweed did spread out and, in this trial, *Saccharina* showed the best growth with over 12 kg/m, the highest recorded at Lehanagh Pool.

Measurements of seaweed morphology showed that in stock 2020-2022 *Alaria* performed consistently (Figure 36), however in stock 2023 loner fronds were. The largest fronds of *Alaria* were recorded as >2100 mm in stock 2023, these were situated on the LTG. *Saccharina* showed an increase in frond length in each trial. The largest fronds were measured in stock 2023 with >1800 mm and also situated on the LTG.

Figure 36. Frond length (mm) of *Alaria esculenta* and *Saccharina latissima* throughout growing periods for each stock 2021 – 2022.

Nutritional components of both species of kelp were analysed at peak biomass from 2023 stock. *Alaria* contained the highest amount of energy and protein (Table 6), whereas *Saccharina* had a greater amount of carbohydrate and NaCl content. Both species had a comparative amount of moisture and ash.

Table 6. Nutrient components of kelp wet weight grown on LTG.

Nutrition	g/100g Saccharina	g/100g Alaria
Energy kcal	14	17
Energy KJ	59	70
Protein	1.1	2.0
Total fat	<0.5	<0.5
Carbohydrate	1.43	<1.0
NaCl	0.94	0.84
Moisture	91.7	91.6
Ash	3.8	3.5

4.3.4 Discussion and Conclusion

The overall results showed that these species of kelp can grow well in an open water system and should be considered as part of an IMTA approach. However, there are some common issues when growing seaweed. For example, crossed lines can be caused by heavy weather or when sampling and interacting with longlines. Heavy fouling will compete for space on longlines against seeded material. Fouling should be removed and re-purposed. Stock should be harvested prior to the onset of heavy biofouling. Abrasion on lines can be caused by incorrectly tied floats and sinkers can cause running on longlines, stripping lines of seeded material and seaweed. Ocean derived debris and large floating seaweed mats can entangle with floats and seaweed lines effecting buoyancy or damaging crops. If significant, this additional pressure can compromise the mooring system. Damage to lines from vessels can occur, therefore seeded areas should be well marked and visible. Heavy weather, old gear, catastrophic failures can result in damage and breakages to the seaweed systems. One if not all of these issues were experienced during the study period. Uniform growth of seaweed was not experienced on growing lines due to one or more of these issues. However, each growing season provided important information on trying to achieve the optimal methodology. ASTRAL Deliverable 2.8 examines the optimal ways to grow seaweed at open sites and draws from the experiences of these trials.

Time of harvest is an important threshold depending on what the seaweed is to be used for (e.g. animal feed, fertilizer or human consumption). If it is destined for the food industry, a clean crop free of biofouling or rot is important. In these trials it was found that April/May was the latest these species

could be left without either biofouling or rot occurring in a detrimental way. It was also determined to be the time of peak biomass.

Comparison of nutritional content found in *Alaria* and *Saccharina* found some values to be similar to those found in Scottish waters¹⁶ and some differentiation. For example, protein content g/100g of fresh seaweed was found to be comparable at 2.44 and 1.4 of *Alaria* and *Saccharina* in Scotland to 1.1 and 2.0 at Lehanagh Pool. However, in Scotland carbohydrate was found at a much higher value than in this study, with 14.64 and 6.93 g/100g compared to 1.43 and <1.0 in Lehanagh Pool. Further work on nutritional content along the growth cycle of these seaweeds would be important to industry in order to understand when best to harvest in relation to use.

The cultivation environment, growing structures and location of this IMTA system along with the combination of other trophic species are suitable for the successful growth of these species of seaweed. These species add to the circular nature of open water IMTA. These species also have a commercial value, they are fast growing and in market demand. For more information on these candidate species please see the 'Species of the Future Catalogue,' ASTRAL deliverable D2.7.

¹⁶ Lytou, A.E.; Schoina, E.; Liu, Y.; Michalek, K.; Stanley, M.S.; Panagou, E.Z.; Nychas, G.-J.E. Quality and Safety Assessment of Edible Seaweeds *Alaria esculenta* and *Saccharina latissima* Cultivated in Scotland. *Foods* 2021, 10, 2210. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10092210>

4.4 Sea Urchin *Paracentrotus lividus*

4.4.1 Introduction

Sea urchin roe is regarded as a luxury food item and is marketed heavily in Japan and Europe as part of the sushi industry. The Japanese market consumes the largest quantity of roe at about 80-90 % or 50,000 tonnes of the global supply, whereas the European market is estimated to have a market of approximately 3000-3500 tonnes of whole urchin¹⁷. Most sea urchin fisheries are found in temperate regions and tend to focus on a small number of genera, the world's largest producer is Chile with landings half the world's total¹⁸.

The purple sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus* is native to the west coast of Ireland and is distributed in the Mediterranean Sea and along the North-eastern Atlantic from Scotland and Ireland to Morocco¹⁹. In some of its region, populations of the purple sea urchin have come under increased pressure due to overfishing, especially in the Mediterranean^{20,21}. Hatchery-reared stock may become an important resource in the restocking of overexploited populations²².

Environmental factors influencing sea urchin growth mainly relates to water temperature, food quantity and quality and photoperiod⁵. In temperate regions, growth is seasonal with an increase usually occurring in the warmer spring and summer months, optimal temperatures for growth can range from 7 to 22 °C²³. Commercial size of the purple sea urchin is a minimum of 5 cm in diameter²⁴, with the urchin having reached maturity and developed sufficient gonadal tissue for the seafood market. Bringing hatchery-reared sea urchin to market size has the potential to be developed in open water systems such as IMTA production systems. Studies have shown the benefit of co-cultivation of salmon and urchin both on the uptake of particulate matter created by fish feed and somatic and gonadal growth of the urchin²⁵ as well as the fatty acid concentration of the urchin's gonadal tissue²⁶.

¹⁷ Stefánsson, G., Kristinsson, H., Ziemer, N., Hannon, C., & James, P. (2017). Markets for sea urchins: a review of global supply and markets. *Skýrsla Matís*, 45, 10-17.

¹⁸ Andrew, N. L., Agatsuma, Y., Ballesteros, E., Bazhin, A. G., Creaser, E. P., Barnes, D. K. A., ... & Xiaoqi, Z. (2002). Status and management of world sea urchin fisheries. *Oceanography and marine biology*, 40(40), 343-425.

¹⁹ Boudouresque, C. F., & Verlaque, M. (2001). Ecology of *Paracentrotus lividus*. *Edible Sea Urchins: Biology and Ecology*, 177-216.

²⁰ FAO. Food and Agriculture Organization Fisheries Statistics. (2016).

²¹ Pais, A., Chessa, L. A., Serra, S., Ruiu, A., Meloni, G., & Donno, Y. (2007). The impact of commercial and recreational harvesting for *Paracentrotus lividus* on shallow rocky reef sea urchin communities in North-western Sardinia, Italy. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 73(3-4), 589-597.

²² Giglioli, A. A., Addis, P., Pasquini, V., Secci, M., & Hannon, C. (2021). First assessment of restocking efficacy of the depleted sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus* populations in two contrasted sites. *Aquaculture Research*, 52(6), 2896-2900.

²³ Boudouresque, C. F., & Verlaque, M. (2001). Ecology of *Paracentrotus lividus*. *Edible Sea Urchins: Biology and Ecology*, 177-216.

²⁴ Farina, S., Baroli, M., Brundu, R., Conforti, A., Cucco, A., De Falco, G., ... & Brambilla, W. (2020). The challenge of managing the commercial harvesting of the sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus*: advanced approaches are required. *PeerJ*, 8, e10093.

²⁵ Kelly, M.S., Brodie, C.C., McKenzie, J.D., 1998. Somatic and gonadal growth of the sea urchin *Psammechinus miliaris* (Gmelin) maintained in polyculture with the Atlantic salmon. *J. Shellfish Res.* 17, 1557-1562

²⁶ Cook, E. J., & Kelly, M. S. (2007). Enhanced production of the sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus* in integrated open-water cultivation with Atlantic salmon *Salmo salar*. *Aquaculture*, 273(4), 573-585.

In IMTA systems which include seaweed production, the sea urchin can be fed with these stocks, thus enhancing the circulatory of the IMTA system further, this is the case at Lehanagh Pool.

4.4.2 Trial Methodology

The aim of this trial was to validate sea urchin as a potential IMTA species and test whether urchin can grow in the ASTRAL LTG and to test various growing structures on the growth and mortality of urchin. In this study, purple sea urchins were grown in structures suspended from longlines located on the LTG. For this small-scale trial juveniles were collected from a sheltered bay and transported to Lehanagh Pool Marine Research site. Transportation can cause stress for the animals, therefore individual urchins were not initially measured and instead counted into growing structures as efficiently as possible. Stock was introduced to the site in March 2021 (100 individuals), stock was counted and checked every month until June 2022. Urchins were fed every 2 weeks from kelp species *Alaria esculenta* and *Saccharina latissima* also grown on site, completing the circularity of the IMTA system. In January 2022, 10 individual's teste (spherical hard shells) diameter (mm) was measured from each growing structure. Two growing structures were trialed: HDPE barrels and Hexcyl baskets (Figure 37).

Figure 37. HDPE barrel and urchin on kelp inside barrel (top), Hexcyl baskets and urchin (bottom).

HDPE barrels were approximately 40 cm in diameter with a height of 80 cm. Hexcyl baskets were 25 l baskets, 73.2 cm in length, 27 cm width and 14 cm height.

Refer to D2.8 for further details on cultivating sea urchin in an open water system.

4.4.3 Results

Total mortality for the barrel growing structure was 56.9 %, a combined mortality recorded in Hexcyl baskets was 12.5 %. The largest mortality was recorded after storm events. All the growing structures tested produced sea urchin to market size; urchin in Hexcyl 1 growing structures showed a slightly larger size range (58.21 - 75.31 mm) than other structures (Figure 38).

Figure 38. Boxplot showing size range in teste diameter (mm) for urchin in each growing structure.

4.4.4 Discussion and Conclusion

This study showed that growing purple sea urchins close to the proximity of salmon cages is a viable option for IMTA open water production in a sheltered bay. Using growing structures designed primarily for molluscs such as the Hexcyl baskets showed that *Paracentrotus lividus* can be grown successfully if the structures are maintained on a regular basis, other structures such as the barrel design did not work well with a higher mortality recorded in these structures. During this study, two types of kelp species were fed to the urchin from those being grown onsite (*Alaria esculenta* and *Saccharina latissima*). The use of this kelp also provided a physical buffer to the urchin within the growing structures in bad weather. Studies have shown that temperature and the amount and type of feed can

have a big impact on the gonadal development^{27, 28, 29}. A follow-up study on what algal species to best use as feed and its impact on somatic growth of purple sea urchins in open water systems could provide valuable information to commercial cultivation of this species. Due to the limited number of available individuals this was not feasible for this study.

Further trials of the purple sea urchin were intended during the ASTRAL project; however, sourcing of juvenile stock was a limiting factor. Ideally, a juvenile stock would be acquired from hatcheries, put to sea and then on-grown in the IMTA system. Harvesting urchin from the wild although not prohibited has been shown to have negative effects on wild populations^{30, 31}.

Another limiting factor to this study was difficulties with nutritional analysis of this species due to technical issues with laboratories and the limited number of individuals in the trial. In-depth nutritional analysis at intervals during the production cycle would be a value undertaking in future trials.

Although there were limiting factors in sea urchin trials for the ASTRAL project, it can be concluded that purple sea urchin can be grown on an open water IMTA system. The increasing demand for sea urchin as a food source makes this species important for the aquaculture industry and an ideal IMTA species due to their role in the circularity of the system.

The cultivation environment, growing structures (Hexcyl baskets) and location of this IMTA system along with the combination of other trophic species are suitable for the successful growth of this species of sea urchin. This species adds to the circular nature of open water IMTA. This species also has a commercial value, it is fast growing and in market demand. However, in the case of this open water system there is a lack of a hatchery source of juveniles to be on-grown at sea. For more information on this candidate species please see the 'Species of the Future Catalogue,' D2.7 for more information.

²⁷ McCarron, E., Burnell, G., & Mouzakitis, G. (2009). Growth assessment on three size classes of the purple sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus* using continuous and intermittent feeding regimes. *Aquaculture*, 288(1-2), 83-91.

²⁸ Santos, P. M., Albano, P., Raposo, A., Ferreira, S. M., Costa, J. L., & Pombo, A. (2020). The effect of temperature on somatic and gonadal development of the sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus* (Lamarck, 1816). *Aquaculture*, 528, 735487.

²⁹ Lourenço, S., Cunha, B., Raposo, A., Neves, M., Santos, P. M., Gomes, A. S., ... & Pombo, A. (2021). Somatic growth and gonadal development of *Paracentrotus lividus* (Lamarck, 1816) fed with diets of different ingredient sources. *Aquaculture*, 539, 736589.

³⁰ Pais, A., Chessa, L. A., Serra, S., Ruiu, A., Meloni, G., & Donno, Y. (2007). The impact of commercial and recreational harvesting for *Paracentrotus lividus* on shallow rocky reef sea urchin communities in North-western Sardinia, Italy. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 73(3-4), 589-597.

³¹ Boudouresque, C. F., & Verlaque, M. (2001). Ecology of *Paracentrotus lividus*. *Developments in aquaculture and fisheries science*, 32, 177-216.

4.5 Lobsters *Homarus gammarus*

4.5.1 Introduction

The European lobster *Homarus gammarus* is an economically important species with a worldwide market size of 63.8 Kilo tonnes (kt) in 2023 and an expected market growth from 2024-2032 of 3.6 %³². With high demand for lobster set to increase, wild stocks are now unsurprisingly reported as decreasing³³. Research into mitigating this effect by releasing hatchery-reared juvenile lobster to restock areas have found juveniles to be more susceptible to predation³⁴. However, other studies have improved survival by using containers housing juvenile lobsters at sea before their final release^{35, 36}. Juvenile lobster feed on zooplankton and organic material suspended in the water column. Lobsters have been shown to work well in an IMTA set-up⁹ with Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) as the fed species producing nutrient rich particulate waste from uneaten food and faecal matter from which lobsters can find a regular food source. Providing this shelter and food supply may have benefits for rewilding/restocking initiatives with further research required.

4.5.2 Trial Methodology

The aim of this study was the cultivation of the European lobster, *Homarus gammarus*. European lobster has been successfully cultivated at the Lehanagh Pool research site and identified as a novel species in IMTA cultivation systems. Co-culture contributes to the utilisation of previously wasted nutrients and release of larger juveniles has been found to increase survivability as a restocking candidate to support local coastal industries.

Lobsters were stocked in individual containers within SBCC structures³⁷ (Figure 39). SBCC units were stocked at 18 individuals per unit and suspended from the LTG grid at three depths (5, 10 and 15 m). A total of 167 lobsters were deployed in November and December 2021. Final sampling of the remaining lobsters was conducted in October 2023. Lobsters were sampled every 6 months, two

³² IMARC Group. Europe Lobster Market Report by Species (American Lobster, Spiny Lobster, Rock Lobster, European Lobster), Weight (0.5 - 0.75 lbs, 0.76 - 3.0 lbs, Over 3 lbs), Product Type (Whole Lobster, Lobster Tail, Lobster Meat, Lobster Claw), Distribution Channel (Food Service, Retail), and Country 2024-2032. <https://www.imarcgroup.com/europe-lobster-market>

³³ Nillos Kleiven P, Espeland S, Olsen E, Abesamis R, Moland E, Kleiven A (2019) Fishing pressure impacts the abundance gradient of European lobsters across the borders of a newly established marine protected area. *Proc R Soc B* 286: 20182455

³⁴ Agnalt, A. L., Grefsrud, E. S., Farestveit, E., & Jørstad, K. E. (2017). Training camp—A way to improve survival in European lobster juveniles?. *Fisheries Research*, 186, 531-537.

³⁵ Halswell P, Daniels C, Johanning L (2018) Framework for evaluating external and internal parameters associated with Sea Based Container Culture (SBCC):towards understanding rearing success in European lobsters (*Homarus gammarus*). *Aquacult Eng* 83: 109–119

³⁶ Daniels C, Wills B, Ruiz-Perez M, Miles E, Wilson R, Boothroyd D (2015) Development of sea-based container culture for rearing European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) around South West England. *Aquaculture* 448: 186–195

³⁷ Halswell, Peter, Carly L. Daniels, and Lars Johanning. "Sea based container culture (SBCC) hydrodynamic design assessment for European lobsters (*Homarus gammarus*)." *Aquacultural engineering* 74 (2016): 157-173.

sampling periods in 2022 and two in 2023. During sampling, each individual container was examined, the lobsters were photographed on gridded paper and weighed when weather conditions allowed. Carapace length was measured using image analysis software; ImageJ (See Appendix 1).

For further information on the cultivation of juvenile lobster at sea, refer to ASTRAL Deliverable 2.8.

Figure 39. Suspended SBCC basket containing layers for lobsters (A) and a lobster on gridded paper for morphology analysis (B).

4.5.3 Results

All juvenile lobsters at every depth (5, 10 and 15 m) showed an increase in weight and length, overall initial mean weight was 0.12 ± 0.03 g and final overall mean weight was 1.73 ± 0.58 g, an increase of 1.61 g (Table 7). Those individuals at 5 m depth displayed the highest growth, measuring twice the size of carapace length two years after they were deployed. The individuals at this depth also showed the highest survival rate.

Table 7. Preliminary results of lobster growth at Lehanagh Pool at 5m, 10m and 15m depth.

Parameters	Units	5m		10m		15m		Overall	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Initial mean weight	g lobster ⁻¹							0.12	0.03
Final weight	g lobster ⁻¹	2.12	0.46	1.32	0.43	1.63	0.71	1.73	0.58
Weight gain	g lobster ⁻¹	1.99	0.46	1.19	0.43	1.50	0.71	1.65	0.59
Percentage weight gain	%	1601.7	372.7	958.4	341.9	1206.7	572.1	1290.7	477.6
Specific Growth Rate	days %	0.39	0.02	0.32	0.05	0.35	0.06	0.36	0.05
Initial carapace length	cm lobster ⁻¹	0.78	0.13	0.82	0.19	1.07	0.24	0.92	0.23
Final carapace length	cm lobster ⁻¹	1.85	0.14	1.68	0.19	1.71	0.21	1.77	0.18
Length gain	cm lobster ⁻¹	1.08	0.27	0.85	0.23	0.64	0.44	0.90	0.34
Percentage length gain	%	149.3	60.6	115.1	59.1	72.6	72.3	119.4	66.7
Survival	%	2.3	0.6	1.7	1.2	2.0	1.4	11.8	

All DO data at each sampling location and depth can be found on Zenodo SharePoint at:

<https://zenodo.org/records/12187427>

4.5.4 Discussion and Conclusion

Survival of juvenile lobsters was very low in this study, with a survival range of 1.4 - 2.3 % between cultivation depths. The most likely causes of this low survival was either low nutritional content available or predation. Biofouling is a major problem at this site and during warmer months, when units are subject to high amounts of coverage (Figure 40). Biofouling can provide a food source to the juvenile lobster along with waste from the salmon pens. However, predation seems to be the most likely cause, based on the lack of carapace remains of individuals in growing containers. When juvenile lobsters moult they are particularly vulnerable to predation from any predatory species able to access these units. Escapement was ruled out as a potential cause as there was no means of escape for the lobsters from the SBCC units.

Figure 40. Example of biofouling during August 2023 sampling.

Despite the low survival rate, juvenile lobsters did show an increase in growth with the best growth rate at 5 m depth. The trial was carried out over a two-year period, other studies have shown survival rates to be a lot higher but length of these studies were a lot shorter^{38, 39}, hence it is difficult to draw comparisons between survival rates. This warrants the question, what is the optimal amount of time to grow juvenile lobsters in SBCC units before release into the wild? Juvenile lobsters are typically grown in the hatchery until life stage V⁴⁰, before transfer to on-growing sites, more work is needed to determine the optimal cultivation periods and the timings for release in stock enhancement programmes. As lobster take a minimum of four years to reach market size (87 – 127 mm carapace length), this lengthy time period means it is not considered a potentially viable aquaculture species. However, stock enhancement measures could be a feasible option in IMTA in areas that have established lobster fisheries that may experience fishing pressures. More research is required on survival rates of this species post release, this could potentially be done by means of temporal and spatial telemetry assessments following further trials at aquaculture facilities. The supply of berried lobster to provide for the hatchery production cycle is also a limiting factor for this type of production and would require the correct permissions to obtain berried lobster from the wild.

Research work is being carried out to conserve the European lobster and enhance stocks e.g. <https://nationallobsterhatchery.co.uk/>, this could be replicated in other areas if funding were in place.

³⁸ http://www.aquaeolas.com/?page_id=537

³⁹ Daniels, C. L., Wills, B., Ruiz-Perez, M., Miles, E., Wilson, R. W., & Boothroyd, D. (2015). Development of sea based container culture for rearing European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) around South West England. *Aquaculture*, 448, 186-195.

⁴⁰ Browne, R., Pérez Benavente, G., Uglem, I., & Carlos Mariño Balsa, J. (2009). An illustrated hatchery guide for the production of clawed lobsters. *Using a Green Water Technique*. Dún Laoghaire: Bord Iascaigh Mhara.

4.6 King scallop *Pecten maximus*

4.6.1 Introduction

There are over 400 species of scallop identified worldwide, these filter feeding bivalves can inhabit substrates from shallow coastal waters to deep seabeds. Scallops are an important resource to the seafood market, global farmed scallop production in 2018 amounted to 2.12 million tonnes with a value of USD 5.8 billion⁴¹. Scallops are most traditionally harvested using scallop dredges or bottom trawls which can damage the seafloor.

Scallop aquaculture developed in Japan in the 1970s and has been fundamental in the development of its aquaculture in several European countries. The main species of interest have been the King scallop *Pecten maximus*, the queen scallop *Aequipecten opercularis* and the black/variegated scallop *Mimachlamys varia*⁴². Their use in IMTA systems has been trialled and *P. maximus* suggested as a candidate for IMTA at finfish farms in Norway⁴³ where, fatty acid profiling showed that scallops have the potential to utilise small particles of waste, salmon feed and faeces.

4.6.2 Trial Methodology

The aim of this trial was to validate the inclusion of the King scallop in an open water IMTA system and to assess the nutritional content of King scallop grown close to salmon pens. Stock was sourced from a commercial scallop producer in the NW of Ireland. A stock of 946 scallop were introduced to the site in January 2021 in lantern nets at no more than 10-15 scallops per layer (Figure 41). Lantern nets were submerged from longlines situated on the LTG at a depth of 2 m below the surface to avoid influence of freshwater at the Lehanagh Pool site. Stock was fully checked approximately every 3 months, this included stock health, morbidity and signs of damage to nets. Biofouling was removed and a subset of a minimum of 10 individuals taken for morphology and biomass measurements. Shell morphology was measured using a set of callipers and a marine scale; height (mm), length (mm) and weight (grams) were recorded (see Figure 42).

⁴¹ ASC website. <https://asc-aqua.org/learn-about-seafood-farming/farmed-scallops/>

⁴² Øivind Strand, Angeles Louro, and Peter F. Duncan, European Aquaculture. In: SANDRA E. SHUMWAY and G. JAY PARSONS, editors, *Scallops*, 3E. Oxford: Elsevier Science, 2016, pp. 859-890. ISBN: 978-0-444-62710-0. Copyright © 2016 Elsevier B.V. Elsevier Sci

⁴³ Bergvik M, Stensås L, Handå A, Reitan KI, Strand Ø and Olsen Y (2019) Incorporation of Feed and Fecal Waste From Salmon Aquaculture in Great Scallops (*Pecten maximus*) Co-fed by Different Algal Concentrations. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 5:524. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2018.00524

Figure 41. Lantern nets housing scallop at Lehanagh Pool.

Figure 42. Image detailing the orientation of scallop for measurement.

Refer to ASTRAL Deliverable 2.8 for details of scallop culturing methods in an open water system.

The trial ended in October 2022 when a sample of scallops were sent to a certified laboratory for nutritional analysis.

4.6.3 Results

At the start of the trial mass mortality occurred with 561 scallops predated upon. The remaining stock was secured from further predation and a mortality of between 20 – 45 individuals were counted in each sampling period thereafter. Shell height (mm) measured from a random sample of individuals showed an increase in overall size of scallop over the study period (Figure 43). The maximum shell height reached by scallop in this time was 99 mm and total weight (g) was found to have a strong linear relationship with shell height, meaning heavier scallop were found to be larger (Linear regression analysis $F(1,231) = 1565$, $p < 0.001$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.87$). This finding suggests that weight accounts for approximately 87 % of the variance in shell height among sampled scallops. In addition to the regression analysis, a scatterplot with fitted regression line (Figure 44) was examined to ensure model assumptions were met.

Figure 43. Shell height (mm) of randomly sampled scallop in each sampling period.

Figure 44. Scatterplot of scallop weight (g) and shell height (mm) with fitted linear regression line.

Scallops were tested for nutritional content with results shown as g/100g. Scallops grown on site showed high protein and energy content (Table 8).

Table 8. Nutritional content of King scallop as analysed by a certified laboratory.

Nutrition	g/100g
Energy (kcal)	79
Energy (KJ)	351
Protein	13.3
Total fat	1.4
Moisture	79.1
Ash	2.0
Carbohydrates	3.22
Dietary fibre	<0.5

4.6.4 Discussion and Conclusion

Scallops are a highly sought after food item, from spat to market size it can take 3-4 years of growth. A market size for King scallop is approximately >120 mm in shell height, 250 g in live weight and has a

meat yield of 55-60 g⁴⁴. Although, none of the individual scallop grown in Lehanagh Pool reached market size, they showed increased growth over an 18-month period and likely would have reached the required size. Mortality was high initially; this was due to predators able to access scallop through gaps in lantern nets. Once this was fixed, predators could no longer attack nets and mortalities declined.

Nutritional profiling provided important information on how the scallop grown at Lehanagh Pool met industry nutritional references. Although the size of scallop sent for testing were not quite at market size, the results were found to be close to those reported for scallops. Per 100 g the scallops analysed had a good protein content but had not reached those reported, protein was found to be 13.3 g compared to 23.2 g, carbohydrate was 3.22 compared to 3.4 g and energy was 79 kcal compared to 119 kcal reported.

On the basis of this trial ASTRAL would promote the use of King scallops as a candidate species in open water sites. However, in the case of this open water system there is a lack of a hatchery source of juveniles to be on-grown at sea. For more information on this candidate species please see the 'Species of the Future Catalogue,' ASTRAL deliverable D2.7.

⁴⁴ <https://www.seafish.org/document/?id=001E9990-56AE-4BFF-80B4-AC8B8A42C103>

4.7 Black scallop - Cluisins *Mimachlamys varia*

4.7.1 Introduction

Over the past decade investigations have been made in France and Spain into the viability of producing the Black/Variegated scallop, *Mimachlamys varia*, (formerly *Chlamys varia*) (Figure 45) and rearing them in an aquaculture setting⁴⁵. These trials were established as a result of a declining fishery for a high value species. The findings of the investigation in France were mixed. The production of spat of black scallops in large quantities was not deemed problematic, although work was needed to improve survival pre and post deployment at sea. Deployment at oyster beds was deemed unsuitable and was suggested that future on-growing trials be conducted in the open sea in suspension from the surface. The growth observed in that particular trial was deemed too slow for good profitability but highlighted growth figures in the literature which would make them more feasible (35 mm at 15 months). It concluded new trials should be conducted in areas offering better growth without restricting juveniles by lack of food⁴⁵.

Figure 45. Black scallop – *Cluisins Mimachlamys varia*.

In the Basque country, the feasibility of black scallop aquaculture was evaluated using different suspension growing systems on the Basque coast. Juveniles were obtained from a hatchery (23.6 ± 4.1 mm and a mean weight of 2.06 ± 1.09 g) and deployed in oyster cages and pots at two experimental sites: a raft installed in the sheltered waters in a harbour and a longline located at offshore waters, at 2 km from the coast. Black scallops attained commercial size (40 mm) in 8 months in offshore waters and in 10 months in the sheltered harbour waters, reaching a mean final weight of 10.23 g, regardless

⁴⁵ Basuyaux, O., Mounsamy, O., Lefebvre, V. & Gauquelin, T. (2014). *Technical and Economic Feasibility Study of a Black Scallop Farm Chlamys Varia in Lower Normandy*. <https://www.smel.fr/wp-content/uploads/2015/02/rapport-petioncle-2013-avec-page-blanche.pdf>

of the culture system used. Poor survival, attributed to sub-optimal transport conditions, was low after the first months of immersion at both sites (1.9-56.9 %). The highest survival values were observed in scallops reared in pots in offshore waters. This report highlights the need to reduce high mortality to improve the economic feasibility of culturing this species⁴⁶.

A previous trial in Ireland monitored the growth of wild caught black scallops which were placed in lanterns 2 m above the seabed in two different bays in Ireland⁴⁷. Although the focus of the trial was not an assessment of the feasibility of the black scallop for aquaculture, the findings showed growth comparable to France (see Figure 46).

Figure 46. Von Bertalanffy growth curves for *C. varia* ongrown in suspended culture at Inner Roskeeda Bay (LM = 58.5, K = 0.69) and Lough Ine (L[∞] = 72.0, K = 0.76).⁴⁸

The biannual pattern of spawning in black scallop is generally reflected in the pattern of spat settlement in collectors^(49,50). On the west coast of Ireland, where the second spawning usually results in the highest settlements, the higher mean temperatures in July and August appear to be more conducive to larval survival and settlement than the conditions in May and June⁵¹. Burnell found that spat collectors need a period of 2-3 weeks immersion to develop a biofilm before they become attractive for larval settlement of black scallops, after which they continue to attract settlement for several weeks.

⁴⁶ Zorita, I., Rodriguez, J. & Garmendia, J. Database of growth and survival of black scallop (*Mimachlamys varia* (Linnaeus, 1758)) in the Basque coast. *Mendeley Data* 2, (2022).

⁴⁷ Burnell, G. Growth and reproduction of the scallop, *Chlamys varia* (L.), on the west coast of Ireland. (National university of Ireland, 1983).

⁴⁸ Burnell, G. Growth and reproduction of the scallop, *Chlamys varia* (L.), on the west coast of Ireland. (National university of Ireland, 1983).

⁴⁹ Conan, G. & Shafee, M. S. Growth and biannual recruitment of the black scallop *Chlamys varia* (L.) in lanveoc area, Bay of Brest. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 35, 59–71 (1978).

⁵⁰ Burnell, G. Annual variations in the spawning and settlement of the scallop *Chlamys varia* (L.) on the west coast of Ireland. *An international compendium of scallop biology and culture* 47–66 (1991).

⁵¹ Burnell, G. Annual variations in the spawning and settlement of the scallop *Chlamys varia* (L.) on the west coast of Ireland. *An international compendium of scallop biology and culture* 47–66 (1991).

4.7.2 Trial Methodology

In August 2021 spat collectors were deployed at Lehanagh pool, West of Ireland. In January 2022 the spat that had settled were observed (Figure 47), in August 2022 the black scallops were transferred to a two-layer collector for on-growing. Sampling was undertaken in October 2023 when the black scallops were counted and measured (Shell height, mm) (Figure 48).

Figure 47. The underside of the corrugated layer that had been placed in the spat collector, with Black scallop spat attached

Figure 48. The different cohorts of black scallop that settled on the collector

4.7.3 Results

A range (from smallest to largest) of collected spat were measured for shell height (mm) and weight (g) to establish an approximate baseline equation for expected growth (Figure 49) for any future trials.

Figure 49. The height and weight of black scallops from the spat collectors at Lehanagh Pool.

Figure 50. Black scallops from the spat collectors, now on-growing at Lehanagh Pool. Note the different cohorts.

In addition to spat collection, wild black scallops were collected from the intertidal zone and placed in collectors to see how well they would survive and grow (Figure 50Figure 51). The shell height at first annual growth rings were measured from some of these. The annual growth rings demonstrate the biannual spawning events, i.e. Spring & Autumn as described for the black scallops in previous trials in Ireland, France (Figure 52).

Figure 51. Black scallops that had been collected from the intertidal zone and suspended at Lehanagh pool.

Figure 52. Height at first annual growth rings of wild caught black scallops from the Bertraghboy Bay. Biannual spawning pattern apparent from this small analysis.

4.7.4 Discussion

Following preliminary investigations into the production of *Mimachlamys varia* at this IMTA site a future feasibility assessment could be carried out, based on this work to date. Spat collectors could be deployed in Spring and Autumn to target the Spring and Autumn settlements. Collectors could be deployed at different depths to better guide future efforts at spat collection. The collectors should be cleaned regularly as biofouling of sea-squirts is very heavy during the Spring and Summer months at the site. Different containment methods for on-growing could be trialled in an attempt to prevent predation by otters (*Lutra lutra*) present at Lehanagh Pool. More regular samples should be obtained to produce more detailed growth and mortality data.

4.8 Native Oysters *Ostrea edulis*

4.8.1 Introduction

There are more than 12 species of oyster and over 200 different varieties farmed around the world. The two main oyster types used in aquaculture are cupped oysters (*Crassostrea* or *Saccostrea* species) and flat oysters (*Ostreacea* oysters). In Europe, the main farmed species are European flat or native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) and Pacific or rock oyster (*Crassostrea gigas*, renamed *Magallana gigas*). Global oyster production amounted to circa 6.4 million tonnes in 2020; China are the largest producer providing 85% of the total production. The EU is the fifth largest producer of oyster products in the world, France has the largest market and produced 81,000 tonnes in 2020⁵². Ireland exported a total of 9223 tonnes of farmed oysters valued at €45.9 million in 2021⁵³.

In Ireland, oyster farms traditionally cultivate *Crassostrea gigas* using bags on trestles along the shoreline, which can be accessed at low tide. These oysters are reared in hatcheries and then grown-on in the intertidal zone. Slow growing, rock oysters can take 3 years to reach market size (70 mm) and native oysters can take up to 4 years.

As filter feeders, oysters remove particles from the water, a single oyster can filter up to 240 litres of seawater per day⁵⁴. At a local level, this activity can improve water quality, with enhanced levels of denitrification. Its ability to filter particulate matter has also made it a candidate for integrated aquaculture; Mazón-Suástegui et al. (2022)⁵⁵, reported improved growth performance of the oyster *Crassostrea corteziensis* on a Mexican shrimp (*Penaeus vannamei*) farm. The potential of using oysters as a lower trophic species in an IMTA set-up is well documented⁵⁶.

4.8.2 Trial Methodology

This trial aims to assess the native oyster *Ostrea edulis* as a species suitable for IMTA open water system and to compare growth of oysters on a lower trophic grid and a control site.

Native oysters are a protected species in this jurisdiction. To source oysters for this trial, individuals were removed from the local oyster bed, under licence sought in line with the Fisheries Act 2010. In

⁵² EUMOFA 2022, Oyster in the EU case study, price structure in the supply chain, focus on France, Ireland and the Netherlands. www.EUMOFA.EU.

⁵³ BIM 2022, Annual Aquaculture Report, A snapshot of Ireland's aquaculture sector. www.bim.ie

⁵⁴ https://www.tcd.ie/tceh/projects/foodsmartdublin/recipes/Sept_Oyster/HistoryEcology_oyster.php

⁵⁵ Mazón-Suástegui, J. M., Arcos-Ortega, G. F., Contreras-Mendoza, C. N., Medina-Sánchez, J. R., Chávez-Villalba, J., Lodeiros, C., ... & López-Carvallo, J. A. (2022). Enhanced growth of the pleasure oyster *Crassostrea corteziensis* cultured under integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) concept, using farm effluents of shrimp *Penaeus vannamei*. *Aquaculture Research*, 53(15), 5214-5226.

⁵⁶ Barrington, K., Chopin, T. and Robinson, S. 2009. Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) in marine temperate waters. In D. Soto (ed.). *Integrated mariculture: a global review*. FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper. No. 529. Rome, FAO. pp. 7-46.

March 2022, oysters were collected by dredging from the Cashel Bank in Betraghboy Bay ($n = 300$) and transferred to Lehanagh Pool which is in the same bay. One hundred ungraded oysters were placed into three oyster tumblers and suspended from longlines in three locations at the Marine Research site (Figure 53). Two locations, the longline (LL) and LTG were within the circularity of the salmon pens and a control was located away from circularity of salmon pens (Ctrl), at approximately 100 m distance. From March 2022 to March 2023, oysters were routinely counted and measured, height of shell (mm) and wet weight (grams) were recorded. Six of the largest individuals were taken from each sampling period and used as destructive samples in which meat yield could be assessed. Large individuals were selected for maximum meat yield so as not to deplete the numbers of oysters. These samples were taken to the laboratory and weighed and measured for tissue weight (grams). On occasion, oysters would be found shell-bound, meaning they attached to each other; on these occasions, oysters were counted and recorded as shell-bound and left out of analysis. In March 2023, all the remaining oysters ($n = 69$) at the LTG site were sent to a certified laboratory for nutritional analysis. The oysters located at LL location were moved to the LTG site (renamed Relocated) and monitoring of these and those at the Ctrl continued. No destructive samples were taken after March 2023, until the last sampling event in April 2024. At the end of the trial, all relocated oysters were sent to a certified laboratory for nutritional analysis and a comparison was made from the March 2023 sample.

Figure 53. Aerial view of locations of oyster tumblers (Ctrl, LL, and LTG).

For more detailed information of growing native oysters in open water systems refer to D2.8.

4.8.3 Results

In the first four months of oyster monitoring, mortality was low, between 0-7.5 %. The largest amount of mortality recorded on site was in March 2023 with 11.76-27.41 %. The location with the highest oyster mortalities from March 2022 to March 2023 was both the Ctrl and LTG sites with an overall loss of 37 % at each location.

Shell height was used as a measurement for oyster growth, oysters at every location showed an increase over the study period (Figure 54). Unfortunately, the CTRL group was lost after a storm event caused the basket to come away from the longline; no further measurements could be taken after the September 2023 sampling effort for this group.

Figure 54. Shell height (mm) measured in every sampling effort and location group

Over the whole study period, oyster shell height ranged from 15.11 - 92 mm on the LTG (average 59.29 ± 10.53), 18 - 94 mm on the LL (average 60.36 ± 11.00), 25 - 92 mm on the CTRL (average 59.63 ± 12.11) and 43 - 89 mm for Relocated (average 70.37 ± 10.17). Shell growth rate ranged from $-2.33 - 2.52$ mm/month (average) at the LTG location, $-2.05 - 2.33$ mm/month at the LL and Relocated location and $-1.95 - 2.45$ mm/month at the CTRL. The negative values are attributed to the destructive sampling and removal of larger oysters. The largest amount of growth was measured from Spring to early

Autumn months and from late Autumn and Winter months' growth was limited. Of all oysters remaining (Relocated) 39.3 % reached a shell height of ≥ 75 mm after two years of growth in the open water system.

An increase in tissue weight per centimetre of shell height was observed across the study period. Values appear slightly higher at the LL location compared to LTG from July 2022 to January 2023 (Figure 55).

Figure 55. Relative tissue weight (g WWWT/cm SH) for destructive oyster samples in each location group.

Oysters were sent for nutritional analysis one year before end of the trial and at the end of the trial (Table 9). In March 2023 oysters sent had an average shell height of 61.49 ± 7.74 mm compared to those sent in April 2024 which had an average of 69.68 ± 10.05 mm. Oysters sampled in 2024 show a higher energy value and protein content and lower carbohydrate and moisture.

Table 9. Nutritional content of oysters taken one year a part in March 2023 and April 2024.

Nutrition	Value g/100g (Mar-23)	Value g/100g (Apr-24)
Energy (kcal)	76	83
Energy (kJ)	319	351
Protein	10.1	12.4
Total fat	1.6	1.9
Carbohydrates	5.07	4.13
Ash	3.0	3.9
Moisture	80.1	77.7
Fibre	<0.5	<0.5

4.8.4 Discussion and Conclusion

A recent 18-month case-study on flat oysters grown in IMTA conditions in Montenegro⁵⁷ found the oyster mortality to be highest at a site close to fish cages, it was also found to produce the smallest oysters in comparison to 100 m away or in a monoculture system. Overall, this study found mortality to be relatively low and no difference was found between locations. However, fed species were not maintained at commercial levels and predominantly only one sea cage contained salmon during this period. Future studies would benefit from growing oysters in an area in which fed species were kept to commercial levels.

The protozoan *Bonamia ostreae* has had a negative impact on oyster stocks throughout Europe and causing decline of the native oyster in Ireland⁵⁸. For this reason, taking oysters from the wild and bringing them into a new location is problematic. Ideally oysters would be sourced from regulated hatcheries rather than taking stock from the wild and potentially impacting on wild populations. However, the availability of hatcheries that produce juvenile native oysters for this purpose has been difficult and could be a limiting factor in the future.

Another potential limiting factor is the marketability of filter feeding species such as scallop and oyster in IMTA due to stipulations contained in EU Regulation (EC) No. 767/2009⁵⁹ which prohibits the use of animal waste as a food source for any other animal, both for food producing and non-food producing

⁵⁷ Nikolić, S., Mandić, M., Pešić, V., Ikica, Z., & Peraš, I. (2024). Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture of the European flat oyster (*Ostrea edulis* Linnaeus, 1758): A case study from Boka Kotorska Bay (Montenegro). *Oceanological and Hydrobiological Studies*, 53(1).

⁵⁸ Flannery, G., Lynch, S. A., Carlsson, J., Cross, T. F., & Culloty, S. C. (2014). Assessment of the impact of a pathogen, *Bonamia ostreae*, on *Ostrea edulis* oyster stocks with different histories of exposure to the parasite in Ireland. *Aquaculture*, 432, 243-251.

⁵⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:229:0001:0028:EN:PDF>

animals (Article 6, Annex III). This prohibition is a solid barrier to the production of extractive species within IMTA production systems which are co-cultivated with a fed species.

Comparison of the nutritional content of Lehanagh Pool IMTA oysters to published values⁶⁰ shows that Lehanagh Pool samples were displaying standard nutritional values from the first sampling. However, in the last sample sent for analysis at the end of the trial, oysters showed higher values than those published as standard values.

Based on this trial, ASTRAL would promote the use of *Ostrea edulis* as a candidate species in open water sites. However, in the case of this open water system there is a lack of a hatchery source of juveniles to be on-grown at sea. For more information on this candidate species please see the 'Species of the Future Catalogue,' ASTRAL deliverable D2.7.

⁶⁰ Holland, B., Brown, J., & Buss, D.H., 1993. Fish and Fish Products, the third supplement to McCance & Widdowson's The Composition of Foods (5th Edition), HMSO, London

4.9 Sea cucumber *Holothuria forskali*

Sea cucumbers were trialled at Lehanagh Pool as part of the InEval H2020 project⁶¹. The objectives of this project were to investigate the survivability of sea cucumbers at Lehanagh Pool to establish if there would be potential for bioremediation as an ecosystem service. The study was conducted between summer 2021 and summer 2022. The site comprised three polar circle cages (50 m circumference and 8 m deep) at a water depth of 20 m. The sediment at this location is muddy and sandy. The site was managed according to organic farm standards, with no prescription medicines or antifoul used. Sea cucumbers were gathered and weighed before deployment and weight assessments continued bi-monthly. This stock was placed into cages and deployed under salmon pens. Growth and survivability assessments were carried out. Sea cucumbers were stocked at two different densities. Survival rates of the sea cucumbers varied according to location. Stocking densities had an impact on the mortality rates.

Sea cucumber bioremediation has been validated in the lab and in relevant environments⁶². Research has found that individual sea cucumbers have the capacity to ingest up to 15.25 kg dry weight sediment m²/yr and reduce as much as 74 % of organic carbon per mean total drained weight of 196 g⁶³. In the case of sea cucumbers at Lehanagh Pool further investigations and analysis needs to be carried out. As sea cucumber are a novel species to IMTA open water systems, potential bio-remediation has yet to be defined.

⁶¹ InEval H202 project. <https://www.awi.de/en/science/special-groups/aquaculture/aquaculture-research/projects/ineval.html>

⁶² Slater, M. J., & Carton, A. G. (2009). Effect of sea cucumber (*Australostichopus mollis*) grazing on coastal sediments impacted by mussel farm deposition. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 58, 1123-1129.

⁶³ Neofitou, N., Lolas, A., Ballios, I., Skordas, K., Tziantziou, L., Vafidis, D., 2019. Contribution of sea cucumber *Holothuria tubulosa* on organic load reduction from fish farming operation. *Aquaculture* 501, 97-103.

5 ASTRAL IMTA Production Species/Production Value Chain

IMTA Lab Ireland focused on the development and validation of fed and low-trophic species production in an IMTA open water system. During the lifespan of the ASTRAL project, 11 species were trialled at Lehanagh Pool. Growing structures, stocking regimes, survival and growth, health and welfare of these IMTA species were investigated throughout the ASTRAL trials.

Atlantic Salmon - *Salmo salar* stocks grew well throughout each of the trials. Salmon play an important role in the trophic relationships of this open water system as the feed and waste from the salmon form the source of the nutrient flow across the Lehanagh Pool Low Trophic Grid (LTG) system. The positioning of the LTG next to the salmon pens allowed for the flow of nutrients to be targeted towards the lower trophic species.

Both species of cleaner fish Lumpfish *Cyclopterus lumpus* and Ballan wrasse *Labrus bergylta*, grew successfully during the IMTA trials. Their function as biological agents to control seal ice infestations were found to be successful. While not technically an IMTA species and given that the stocking number are low, this species would not directly be categorised as a fed IMTA species in this open water production system however these species play an important role in the health and welfare maintenance of the salmon.

Overall results for *Alaria esculenta* and *Saccharina latissima*, showed that these species of kelp can grow very well on longlines in an LTG, in an open water system and should be considered as valuable contributor to the circularity of this type of IMTA approach.

The cultivation environment, growing structures and location of this IMTA system along with the combination of other trophic species are suitable for the successful growth of the sea urchin – *Paracentrotus lividus*. This species adds to the circular nature of open water IMTA.

Based on these trials, ASTRAL would promote the use of the native oyster, *Ostrea edulis*, as an ideal IMTA candidate species in open water aquaculture production sites.

ASTRAL would also promote the use of King scallops – *Pecten maximus*, in this value chain as a candidate IMTA species in open water sites.

The other species trialed at Lehanagh Pool during this project have shown potential as aquaculture species however, due to various reasons listed below they are not included in the ASTRAL open water value chain as recommended species of the future.

- In the case of the European lobster - *Homarus gammarus* due the longevity of its life cycles, it does not make an ideal candidate for commercial aquaculture.

- There is a paucity of data on the circularity potential the sea cucumber *Holothuria forskali* and more work would be required to assess its place in open water IMTA.
- More work would be required to assess the potential for the Black Scallop (Cluisin) *Mimachlamys varia* as an aquaculture candidate in open water production, if it proved to be a viable aquaculture species it would potentially have a place in future IMTA systems.

Therefore, the recommended open water ASTRAL IMTA species are salmon as the fed species, seaweeds such as kelp, native oyster, sea urchin and king scallop as the extractive species, or combinations of same. These species have been investigated in terms of their circularity performance⁸, which will be further discussed in the ASTRAL Deliverable D2.7.

The trials conducted at IMTA Lab Ireland have provided valuable data on cultivation of IMTA species. Information on the environmental parameters, survival and growth as well as the welfare of selected IMTA species in this IMTA system was generated, which could promote broader uptake of IMTA by local and international producers and enhance the sustainability of these production species and value chain. These findings have contributed towards the development of new, sustainable, profitable and resilient value chains for IMTA production within ASTRAL and the framework of existing, emerging and potential Atlantic markets.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

Methodology for ImageJ software to measure lobster carapace.

How to use ImageJ software:

- Download and open ImageJ software.
- Set the scale. Select the line measuring tool.>Measure a square of the grid> Draw a line across> Press Ctrl+M> Repeat 10 times at random. Measure both horizontally and vertically. Hold the shift button while measuring to draw a straight line.
- Once 10 measurements are taken>Select Analyses>Summary>This will give the mean length in Pixels.
- Once the mean length of the grid in Pixels is acquired; Select Analyse>Select Set Scale and input values as follows:
In the Set scale menu>In distance in Pixels enter the mean calculated distance in pixels>In Known Distance enter 5 (the grid is 5 mm in length), leave pixel aspect ratio as 1, Unit of length is mm.
- Tick Global (This is important), and select OK.
- The length will now be shown in mm.
- To measure Lobsters >Use the line measuring tool> measure from the back of the eye to the end of the carapace,>measure from the Left eye and Right eye,>Summarise and take the mean length and record.